

Interplay between geometric and dynamic phase in liquid crystals

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As stated by Fermat's principle, light propagation is dictated by the phase of the field. The phase is in turn dependent on the refractive index and its gradient in isotropic media; such a phase is called dynamic. In the presence of more complicated constitutive relationships, other effects contribute to the phase: e.g., in inhomogeneously twisted anisotropic materials, the electromagnetic phase depends also on the local rotation of the dielectric tensor. This is due to the geometric or Pancharatnam-Berry phase, physically related to the changes in the optical polarization [1]. The index gradient and the geometric phase can be interpreted as an effective electric and magnetic field acting on the photons respectively, and stemming from the light-matter interaction.

Here, we investigate the reciprocal interaction between geometric and dynamic phase in a bulk material, i.e., such that the propagation distance is much longer than the Rayleigh length of the incident beam. We chose nematic liquid crystals (NLCs) as the experimental platform. NLCs are uniaxial media, and their optical axis can be rotated via external stimuli [2,3]. In our (nonlinear) case, the optical beam itself rotates the NLC optical axis by inducing dipoles in the molecules. NLC planar cells have been used to investigate the self-trapping of light both due to the dynamic [2] and geometric phase [3] separately, but an investigation of the joint action is missing. On the other side, the interplay between the two phases have been investigated only in very thin samples [1,4].

Figure 1(a,b) summarize the relationship between the rotation of the optical axis and the imparted phase on the beam. If the optical axis rotates on the same plane of wavevector and electric field, only the dynamic phase is modulated transversely. Sole action of geometric phase occurs when the rotation occurs on the plane normal to the wavevector. We consider a planar NLC cell subject to a variable bias, the latter moving the optical axis on the plane xz . When the input field is polarized along \hat{x} , only gradients in the dynamic phase are written [Fig. 1(a)]. Transverse modulation of the geometric phase appears when the input beam has a non-vanishing component along \hat{y} [Fig. 1(b)]. Accordingly, maximum self-trapping is achieved for a linearly polarized input parallel to x for low bias, whereas for higher voltages the maximum is achieved for diagonal polarizations [Fig. 1(c-d)]. By varying the bias, the relative weight of geometric and dynamic contributions can be controlled. For intermediate values a more complex trend is observed, the latter being determined by the reciprocal interaction of the two phenomena.

Fig. 1 (a) and (b) show the optical axis distribution in the case of purely dynamic and geometric phase gradients, respectively. (c) and (d) show the observed light propagation for a sinusoidal voltage of amplitude 2.5 and 5V, respectively.

References

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